

precipitated was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol as yellow crystals, $C_{16}H_{15}N_3O_2$, m.p. 110° (Calcd: C, 64.64; H, 5.05; N, 14.14; O, 16.16%).

4-Arylazo-5-methyl-3-aminophenylisoxazole: Appropriate derivative of 1-aminophenyl-3-arylhydrazono-butane-1,3-dione* (0.01 mol) was refluxed with hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.01 ml) in alcohol (25 ml) and sodium acetate (2.0 g) for 4 h. The product after cooling was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from dimethylformamide, m.p. 88° (Found: N, 20.01; C, 69.00; H, 4.70. $C_{16}H_{14}N_4O$ calcd. for: N, 20.14; C, 69.06; H, 5.00%); λ_{max} (CH₃OH) 400 nm (N=N); M^+ at *m/e* 278; ν_{max} (KBr) 1595 (N=N), 1610 (C=C or C=N); 3415 (NH) and 750–800 cm^{-1} (substituted phenyl); a sharp singlet at δ 2.5 (3H, 3CH₃), one signal at δ 3.0 (1H, NH) and a group of signals at δ 7.5–8.0 (10H, 2C₆H₅) were also observed.

Similarly other substituted azo compounds having substituents 2-OH, 2-OCH₃, 2-Cl, 4-Cl, 2-CH₃, 4-CH₃, 4-CH₃-3-NO₂, 4-Cl-2-NO₂, 3-NO₂, 4-NO₂, and 4-Br were prepared by taking suitable hydrazone. One more series of compounds, viz. 4-arylazo-5-methyl-3-amino(2-chlorophenyl)isoxazoles were prepared by the similar method. Characteristics of the synthesised compounds are given in Table 1.

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Synthesis of [S-(2-Acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)]-N-aryldithiocarbamates

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MANY 2,5-disubstituted-1,3,4-oxadiazoles have been reported to possess various biological activities¹⁻³. Dithiocarbamates themselves and their incorporation with various heterocyclic moieties lead to some important biologically active agents⁴. Keeping this in view, we have studied synthesis and antimicrobial activities of some [S-(2-acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)]-N-aryldithiocarbamates. The compounds were synthesised as shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1: Reagents: (i) ONBr, K₂CO₃, (ii) ClCH₂COCl, C₆H₆, (iii) NH₄-S-CS-NHR.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Purity of the synthesised compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. The structures of the compounds were established on the basis of their elemental analysis, counter synthesis, m.m.p. and ir spectra. The ir spectra of the compounds showing characteristic band at 1280 (N=N=C), 1520 (C=N cyclic), 1320 (pentacyclic ring), 1740 (C=O), 3260–3340 (NH; str), 1650 (CO=N), 1160 (C=S) and 740 cm^{-1} (ortho-disubstituted benzene), supported the validity of the compounds.

2-Amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazoles (1): It was prepared by following the reported method⁵.

2-Chloroacetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (2): It was chloroacetylated by the reported procedure⁶.

Ammonium aryldithiocarbamate : The compounds were prepared by the reported method⁶.

S-(2-Acetyl-amino-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazolyl)-N-aryldithiocarbamates (3) : A mixture of 2-chloro-acetamido-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole (0.01 mol) and ammonium aryldithiocarbamate (0.01 mol) in dry acetone was stirred for 0.5 h at room temperature and then refluxed for 90 min. Excess of solvent was then distilled off, the solid product washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol (Table 1).

Pharmacological screening : The compounds were screened for antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* and *E. coli*. Representative compounds were screened for antitubercular activity against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇R_v).

Results and Discussion

Antibacterial activity : Out of fifteen compounds, seven compounds were found to be active against *S. aureus* and eight compounds active against *E. coli*; and five compounds active against both the species. Compound having 4-chloro substitution was most active against both the species. Moreover, compounds having 4-methyl, 4-methoxy, 4-ethoxy and 3-nitro substitutions were also active against both the species but their activity being low this details of biological activity are not reported.

Antitubercular activity : The compounds showed poor antitubercular activity. Out of five compounds, not a single compound was effective at lower concentration (35 µg ml⁻¹). But two compounds, having 2,3-dimethyl and 3-nitro substitutions were found effective at higher concentration (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, PHYSICAL AND BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY DATA OF 1,3,4-OXADIAZOLES

Sl. no.	R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
1.	2-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	162	52
2.	3-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	144	52
3.	4-OH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	196	50
4.	2-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	142	59
5.	3-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	166	54
6.	4-OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	127	56
7.	2,3-(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	136	47
8.	2,4-(OH) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	145	56
9.	2-O ₂ C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	136	54
10.	4-O ₂ C ₂ H ₅ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	117	52
11.	2-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	166	57
12.	3-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	128	61
13.	4-Cl-C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClN ₄ O ₂ S ₂	106	59
14.	2-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	140	64
15.	3-NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	151	61

*N and S analyses found satisfactory.

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Synthesis of 2-(2-Amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones

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4-THIAZOLIDINONE derivatives are known to possess a variety of physiological properties¹. These reports prompted us to synthesise a series of hitherto unreported 2-(2-amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones.

The required 2-aminonicotinaldehyde hydrazones (3) were prepared by the condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde (1) with aromatic acid hydrazides (2) in ethanol in the presence of a few drops of glacial acetic acid². The cyclocondensation of thioglycolic acid with these hydrazones led to the formation of 2-(2-amino-3-pyridyl)-3-substituted-benzoylamino-4-thiazolidinones (4) in DMF containing anhydrous ZnCl₂ (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds were determined by elemental analyses and ir spectral data. The ir spectra of 4 exhibited characteristic bands at 3 430 (NH), 2 930